

INDIVIDUAL APPROACH IN EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article examines the necessity of organizing individual educational work with children, emphasizing the importance of understanding their key mental and physiological characteristics. Particular attention is given to the typological features of the nervous system as a primary factor. The relevance of this issue is explained by the fact that in the context of globalization and technological advancement, uniform pedagogical approaches may not be equally effective for children with different types of nervous activity. The research methodology includes analysis, comparison, and empirical approaches. The results demonstrate that an individual approach is one of the fundamental factors in child education. The scientific contribution of the author lies in analyzing psychological factors influencing child development and developing practical recommendations.*

Keywords: *child, education, individuality, methodology, psychological factors, nervous system, approach, learning, society.*

“The most important task of teachers is to provide quality education to the younger generation and raise them as physically and spiritually mature individuals.”

Shavkat Mirziyoyev,

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Introduction

In our country, along with increasing attention to all levels of the continuous education system, including the preschool education stage, the proportion of children enrolled in preschool institutions is gradually decreasing. Conducting targeted research in this area can be considered part of our national scientific and technical program and a priority research direction.

A necessary condition for organizing individual educational work with children is understanding their main mental and physiological characteristics, with primary attention given to the typological features of the nervous system. It is evident that identical pedagogical influences cannot be equally effective for children with different types of nervous activity. For example, a child with a strong nervous system may possess strengths that a child with a weak type does not.

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A child with inert nervous processes may surprise the teacher with their slowness, while a child with excitable and highly mobile processes may constantly be restless. Therefore, educational work with such children must be based on their biological characteristics and aimed at cultivating positive traits. In the case of a child with a weak nervous system, the teacher should gradually increase the workload to enhance the efficiency of the child's nerve cells.

Many representatives of advanced Russian and foreign pedagogy have paid attention to the problem of individual approach in child education. In the pedagogical system of the great Czech teacher Jan Amos Komensky, the principles of teaching and educating children are already built on consideration of age and individual characteristics, identified through systematic observations.

The outstanding Russian educator K.D. Ushinsky developed a broad methodology for individual approach to children, forming the basis for preventive work on developing good habits.

At the same time, he emphasized that no precise recipes can be provided for the complex process of individual approach, highlighting the creative nature of solving this problem.

Problem relevance. Preparing preschool children for school has social and political significance. Therefore, numerous studies in pedagogical theory and practice have addressed this area. For instance, the problem of preparing children for school in the family environment remains highly relevant.

Research objective: To develop methods for implementing an individual-psychological approach to the education of preschool children in preparation for school, as well as to determine requirements for its effectiveness and ways of implementation.

Research object: The process of applying an individual-psychological approach to the education of preschool children in preparation for school and ensuring adherence to it.

Research subject: The theoretical and psychological foundations of the individual approach in the education of preschool children.

Methods used in the study:

Scientific theoretical study and analysis of historical, philosophical, moral, psychological, and pedagogical literature, study of normative documents of preschool education institutions, and educational-methodical manuals;

Observation;

Interview;

Tests;

Generalization of results obtained based on mathematical-statistical analysis.

Research stages: The research is carried out in the following stages.

In the first stage, philosophical, pedagogical, and psychological literature related to the topic is studied; their content is analyzed, the current state of requirements and compliance in the daily schedule for preparing preschool children for school is examined; main theoretical perspectives are summarized, and initial materials are collected to organize experimental-test work.

Scientific novelty of the research:

The theoretical foundations of requirements and methods of compliance for the psychological education of children in preparing them for school in the family, for preschool teachers and parents, are recommended.

Degree of study of the specific features of preschool children in the literature:

The period from 3 to 7 years is considered the preschool age. Taking into account the very rapid qualitative changes in the psychology of preschool children, this period can be divided into three stages:

3–4 years – early preschool period;

4–5 years – middle preschool period (middle kindergarten age);

6–7 years – late preschool period (older kindergarten age).

Significant aspects of taking into account the individual characteristics of preschool children in the educational process

During the process of development, a child enters into a special and unique relationship with the world of objects and phenomena created by previous generations of humans. The child actively assimilates and masters all achievements acquired by humanity. In this process, the child must master the world of objects, the actions performed with them, language, interpersonal relationships, the development of motives for activity, and the growth of abilities, primarily with the direct assistance of adults. Essentially, from this period onward, the child's independent activity begins to strengthen.

Using Methods of Individual-Psychological Approach in the Education of Preschool Children

The psyche indicates the elevation of moral thinking above momentary impulses and needs.

The personal education direction represents a personal method of realizing a child's (student's) individual potential in education and upbringing, which includes:

Intellectual;

Emotional-volitional;

Active;

Moral and spiritual.

The main goal of creating a personal education direction (in preschool educational institutions) is to create conditions that facilitate the positive socialization of preschool children in kindergartens and support their social and personal development. This is organically connected with the overall processes of the child's intellectual, emotional, aesthetic, physical, and other aspects of development.

Using Psychological Trainings in the Activities of Preschool Children

Approximate program for preparing a psychological and pedagogical presentation for a preschool teacher:

1. Section "General Information about the Child":

You should indicate where the child comes from (family, another preschool institution), whether there have been long breaks at the preschool institution or not, and for what reasons.

Assess the child's adaptation to the group: good; satisfactory; insufficient; poor; other.

2. Section "Family Characteristics":

Information about the parents should be provided. Fill in the sections as follows:

Family composition: complete, incomplete, large, presence of brothers and sisters.

Type of family:

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- a) Well-off: parents are morally stable and have a culture of upbringing;
- b) Dysfunctional: pedagogically incapable; lack of unity in parental demands; inattention to the child; cruel treatment; systematic punishment; little information about child's interests or behavior in kindergarten;
- c) Morally defective: parents have an immoral lifestyle, alcoholism, parasitism, criminal records; do not raise children;
- d) Conflictual: dysfunctional emotional environment in the family; disputes; parents are nervous, cruel, uncompromising.

Indicate who educates the child: mother, father, grandmother, or others.

The Nature of Relationships Between Parents and Children

- a) Family Dictate: systematic suppression of the child's initiative and self-respect;
- b) Overprotection: satisfying all the child's needs, protecting them from difficulties, worries, and actions;
- c) Indulgence: avoidance of active participation in the child's upbringing, passivity, recognition of the child's complete autonomy;
- d) Collaboration: mutual respect, shared experience of joy and sorrow.

When discussing the formation of a human personality, it is also necessary to emphasize that certain extraordinary events fully confirm the decisive importance of the external environment in the development of a person. In particular, we consider rare accidental cases where human children fall into the environment of wild animals.

Although such events are very rare in life, they do occur. For example, Dr. Sing from India observed near the forests of Kolkata that two human children were running on all fours together with wolf cubs. He then tracked them, located their shelter, and took the children away. He named one Amala and the other Kamala. It is characteristic that, having grown up in the wolf environment from early childhood, the children did not differ from the wolves in temperament and behavior.

There was no speech; hence, their thinking was extremely limited. The children, who were being re-educated with great difficulty, eventually died from colds in the wolf environment. This case fully confirms that for the development of a human as a personality, the primary environment must be human, i.e., a social environment. The second factor influencing the personality and psychology of a child is the effect of education and upbringing.

ЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЕ

Индивидуализация обучения смягчает разрыв между уровнем, установленным в общей образовательной программе, и объективными возможностями ребенка. В соответствии с государственным образовательным стандартом, целью индивидуальной образовательной линии для ребенка дошкольного возраста является создание мотивации и благоприятных условий для раскрытия интеллекта, эмоциональных, физических и творческих способностей ребенка.

Учебная деятельность должна приносить детям радость, удовольствие и вызывать чувство удовлетворения. С раннего детства важно воспитывать у детей интерес к познанию.

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Поскольку стремление к знанию является значимым мотивом человеческой деятельности, оно отражает осознанность направленности личности, оказывает положительное влияние на все психические процессы и функции, активизирует способности и пробуждает все человеческие силы в условиях наличия интереса. Это особенно необходимо учитывать при организации учебной деятельности ребенка в детском саду.

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